

RUSSIAN OCCUPATION OF TURKMENISTAN

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Since the second half of the nineteenth century, the interests of developing capitalism in Russia required the expansion of sales markets, the seizure of new sources of raw materials. The demand of the Russian textile industry for cotton has gradually increased. During this period, the influence of Russia on the eastern coast of the Caspian Sea intensified day by day. Tsarist Russia, defeated in the Crimean War of 1853-1856, had its eyes on Central Asia after realizing that it could not advance in Europe and the Middle East. Between 1858 and 1860, the Russians reformed their army again, neglecting international relations, and under various pretexts occupied the Turkmen khanates one by one between 1864 and 1873. In 1869, Russian troops built a fortification on the eastern coast of the Caspian and founded the city of Krasnovodsk. By 1885, the entire territory of Turkmenistan was occupied by the Russians.

Keywords: Attack, conquest, fighting heroically, independent, Russian troops.

Introduction. From 1860 to 1864, the Turkmens lived as free sons of an independent homeland until the occupation of The Merv region by the Russians, which was on the territory of Turkmenistan. By order of the commander of the Russian troops, general Kaufman and general Golovatsov, the local Turkmens were seized and their lands were set on fire. Against the invasion of the Russians, the Turkmen Khans fought bravely and organized raids on Russian headquarters. But the attacks of the Turkmens were mercilessly silenced by Russian cannons. The American Gazetteer who watched the Russian invasion wrote about this: "as the Russian troops were advancing in the midst of Human dead and fogs, a group of Turkmen peasants expressed a desire to meet the commander of the troops. With the permission of the commander, the Turkmens came to us. When the Russian commander asked them what they wanted, the Turkmens gave the following answer: "we did not make any attacks against the Russians. Why are Russians occupying our country? We want to find out why. The Russian commander and soldiers could not give any answer to this pure request. Because they themselves could not understand the plans of tsarism to invade"[2, p. 338].

In pursuit of the heavy blows they inflicted on the Turkmens, these invasion forces devised a plan for a new blow. The Turkmens were demanded compensation of 2,200,000 francs. This compensation was much heavier than the compensation demanded by Prussia from France in 1870. Some of the Khiva Turkmens were forced to accept the material and moral blows of the Russians as much as possible. Some, however, did not accept Russian colonization and fled to Turkmenistan, overcoming the Karakum steppe.

The main part. The Russians have been preparing for the attack on the Turkmens since the 1820s and 30s, collecting information about the situation of the Turkmens. Yuzbashi Muravyov traveled to Turkmenistan and Khiva and informed the government about the Turkmens. In 1858, Ignatiev visited the khanates of Central Asia and gave information about the khanates and how these khanates could be occupied. The Russian officer Dandaville arrived in Turkmenistan in 1859

and informed the government that the Kyzylsu fortress on the Caspian coast was of both military and commercial importance. The Russians decided to invade Kyzylsun on the basis of this information they gave. However, the Turkmens also expressed their consent to the use of this fortress as a trade center. However, after the Russians settled in the fortress, they began to invade the Turkmen lands. This invasion of the Russians caused the Turkmens to take up defense. The purpose of the Russians was to occupy Kokand and Bukhara. Then they planned to capture Khiva.

To prevent the Russian invasion, the Yamud Turkmens living in the east of the Caspian Sea rose to fight under the leadership of Nur Verdi Khan. But Russian troops, led by Colonel Stoletov, in the spring of 1871, despite all the resistance of the Turkmens, launched a counterattack and occupied the region of strife, one of the Centers of residence of the Yamud Turks. The Yamud Turkmens suffered heavy losses.

Colonel Stoletov was called to serve in the Caucasus after a while. Colonel Markozov was appointed in his place. The newly minted Russian team took a tougher position. In September 1871, they captured the Turkmen fortresses on all roads leading to the Khiva Khanate by Kyzyl-su and captured the largest centers inhabited by Turkmens until the spring of 1873. The most important of them were Goz-Ata, Chagil, Kam Sebshen, Uzun Kuyu and Sarikamysh.

The Turkmens were very worried about the Russian campaigns to the eastern shores of the Caspian Sea after the invasion of Kokand and Khiva from the Central Asian khanates. Seeing the magnitude of the threat, the Turkmen Khans Nur Verdi Khan, Khiva Khan Sayyid Muhammad Rahimi held a meeting in Khiva, urging the Turkmens to unite against the Russians. After this meeting, the ruler of Khiva, Sayyid Muhammad Rahim, sent two messengers to the Russian headquarters in Orenburg and Tiflis and addressed them with a letter. However, the Russian command did not respond to the Khan's letter, but rather sent a three-article ultimatum with the Russian representative Grand Duke Michail: 1. Khiva Khan will declare that he is a friend of the Russian government by publishing a decree; 2.

All Russian businessmen will be released; 3. The ruler of Khiva will write a letter explaining why he did not respond to the letter of the Turkestan Governor General Kaufman and will apologize. Only then will friendly relations be established with the Khiva Khanate. After this correspondence, Colonel Markozov arrived in Tbilisi and met with Grand Duke Michail, who, having received new instructions, returned to the Raffles in February 1872. Under the new orders, he would seize the eastern coast of the Caspian from spring to autumn 1872 and increase campaigns and raids on the Khiva Khanate. To do this, Colonel Markozov forcibly levied taxes worth 3500 from Yamud Turkmens living on the shores of the Caspian Sea, and destroyed dozens of Turkmens who did not want to pay taxes. Seeing these preparations of the Russians for an invasion, Nur Verdi Khan opposed the Russian invaders, but still retreated in front of the Russian cannons. After the withdrawal of Turkmen Forces, colonel Markozov invaded the Turkmen regions and launched a protracted attack on Khiva, not expecting any interstate rights, in 1873 they occupied Khiva Khanate. In 1874, the Russians created the "Trans-Caspian Region" governorate in connection with the Caucasus governorate and clearly showed their intention to occupy Turkmenistan. This governorship, which the Russians established illegally, after a while began to interfere in the internal affairs of the Turkmens. The Turkmens met these actions of occupation with great indignation. The Turkmen people stood up to fight tirelessly against the merciless invaders. In 1874, the Turkmen Assembly, headed by Nur Verdi Khan, gathered, declaring that they would never accept the power of the Russians. They showed that we must fight against the Russians, who are our religious enemies, to the last drop of blood. The Turkmens, along with making defensive preparations, appealed to the neighboring Muslim brothers for help. They even sent a delegation to the Afghan emirate, which, by the way, was under British protection, expressing their readiness to accept the rule of the Afghans. According to the Turkmens, entering Afghan power meant entering British power. The Turkmens wanted to do so because the Russians did not encroach on Afghanistan because of the British. They assumed that if they entered into an alliance with Afghanistan, the Russians would not occupy it. But from these initiatives they received nothing but promises. The Turkmens, who wanted to get help from the British against the Russian invaders, were unaware of the disgusting colonial policy of the British. Throughout the 19th century, both Russian and British colonialists invaded the peoples of Central and Central Asia to the power of weapons and used them as a raw material base.

In desperation, the Turkmens, forgetting their hostility to the Iranians against the Russian threat, sent a delegation to Tehran in the spring of 1876. As soon as the delegation approached Tehran, the Russian representative Zinoviev issued a note to the Iranian government not to conduct any negotiations with the Turkmens. A week later, in exchange for bribes from the Russian consul Bakuli, the governor of the buzhnurd settlement in Khorasan attacked the Turkmen Obas and killed many Turkmens. As a result of these intrigues, the

Iranian-Turkmen alliance did not take place. After these events, the Turkmens did not enter into relations with Iran again. The Russians portrayed the Turkmens as a varvar tribe, demonstrating to other states that they were right in this occupation. However, before this occupation, Russian merchants traded with the Turkmens through Astrakhan.

Having committed all the mischief, the Russians justified themselves and launched an offensive in the spring of 1877, led by general Lomakin. In the face of the Russian attack, the Turkmens left such border towns as Bami, Burma and Kizil Avrat and retreated to the goy-Tepe fortified fortress. On May 12, 1877, Turkmen forces under the command of Nur Verdi Khan entered the first serious war in Kyzyl-Avrat with the Russian invaders. Although they suffered great losses in the face of the Russian cannons, the Turkmens were not discouraged and attacked the Golden Avrat again on the Russians. However, they were amazed to see that the Russians were not here. Russian troops under the command of General Lomaki were called to the Caucasus against the Ottoman forces. This gave the Turkmen the opportunity to breathe a little. Turkmen pilgrims returning from Mecca gave the news of the beginning of the Ottoman-Russian war Turkmen.

However, with this war ending in February 1878, Russian forces began preparations to march against the Turkmens immediately in March. When the news was received that the Russians would attack both from the Caspian direction and from the Amu-Darya direction, the Turkmens immediately gathered at a council in Merv and began to prepare measures to save the country. Nur Verdi Khan with his 6,000-strong troops stood against the Russian troops, which would go on the offensive in the direction of Amu-Darya. In the West, Verdi Murad Khan, the eldest son of Nur Verdi Khan, with 15,000 troops stood against the attack of general Lazarev. From the Eastern Front to Marw all villages and settlements were evacuated and retreated to the Fortress of Merv. Also, in the West, Villages and settlements along the Caspian coast were to be evacuated and settled in the goy-Tepe fortress, and the enemy was to be met in the goy-Tepe fortress. However, in front of Lazarev's troops, which attacked with powerful weapons along the entire front, the Turkmens retreated, suffering huge losses. Meanwhile, 1879 on August 26, general Lazarev suddenly died of poisoning. He was succeeded by general Lomakin. Lomakin quickly crossed into huchum in all directions, mercilessly plundering all Turkmen villages, and on September 8 reached 20 kilometers of Goy-Tepe. The sky-Hill was an impregnable fortress with intertwined high fortress walls. On September 9, the Russian troops, which went on the offensive, despite the heroic battle of the Turkmens, broke into the Turkmen fortress with the power of cannons, not sparing any child woman. But they could not get the castle. In the face of the militancy of the Turkmens, they were forced to return to their refuge, and then retreat along the Caspian coast. The battle ended with the defeat of the Russians. In this battle, 185 people were killed and 268 were wounded from the Russians. Of the Turkmens, more than 4 thousand

women and children were injured. Despite this, the heroic fighting of the Turkmens and the failure to surrender to the Russian troops caused bewilderment in all Russian and European cities.

In 1880-81, Russian troops under the command of general Skobelev again invaded the Turkmen lands. Meanwhile, Nur Verdi Khan, who heroically defended his homeland from the enemy, suddenly fell ill and died on May 5, 1880. His death shocked the entire Turkmen people. However, quickly taking over themselves, the Turkmens Nur Verdi Khan's youngest son Mahdim began to prepare against new attacks, choosing his slave as Khan. On December 23, 1880, the siege began. Under the leadership of embroidery-Sardar, the Turkmens made several successful attacks against the Russians. But on January 12, 1881, the Russians, having blown up the walls of the fortress, broke through to hujum with three columns (7 thousand people and 79 cannons). On the Blue Hill, with 3 ancient cannons and 5 thousand obsolete rifles, there were about 25 thousand monopoly Turkmen. Having advantages in weapons and organization, the Russian troops managed to break the stubborn resistance of the monopoly and take the fortress. Finally, in 1881, on January 12, they smoked the sky-Hill. The Turkmens suffered 28 thousand human losses. It is said that after the capture of Goytepe, a captured Turkmen was brought to Mikhail Skobelev. The General asks him how many casualties they suffered in this battle. The captured Turkmen answer that only 3 people. Skobelev is indignant, saying that after all, the number of dead Turkmens is large, moreover, almost no one has survived either. And the captive Turkmen again calmly: -well, the dead are 3 people-he says. The Turkmen then adds: "The Dead are the commander Tikma Sardar, Bakhshi (Ashiq) Amangaldi Gonibey and the religious leader of the Turkmen Gurbanmurad Ishan. The location of more than 20 thousand people killed in the sky-Hill will be replenished at the expense of newborns. But these 3 people will not be able to give birth to Turkmens. "

After the sky-Tepe was taken, the resistance of the Turkmens was broken. 6 days later, the Russians occupied Ashgabat with slight losses. Here, by Order of Skobelev, Russian soldiers killed all Turkmen men who were more than ten years old. And in 1884, the Russians occupied Marvi, which was considered the last

impregnable fortress of the Turkmens. Thus, the Russians completed the occupation of Turkmenistan. Let us also say that the Russians occupied Turkmenistan in Central Asia much later than in other regional states. The reason for this was the strong resistance of the Turkmens to the Russian occupation.

Conclusion. The sky-Hill massacre in the history of Turkmenistan stands as a bloody page. The Turkmens cannot forget this massacre and continue to live the tragedy as a historic day hardest in their hearts. In January 1990, President of Turkmenistan Saparmurad Niyazov signed a decree on the annual celebration of the 1881 Goy-Tepe massacre on January 12 as a day of national mourning. The order stated that the purpose of this was not to provoke enmity between Russians and Turkmens, but to commemorate the heroic defenders of Goy-Tepe and 20 thousand Turkmens killed. In this regard, Saparmurad Niyazov said: "it is our sacred duty to commemorate the goy-Tepe tragedy and to commemorate its victims. "

Today, a large mosque is located on the site of the goy-Tepe fortress. Every year on January 12, the national flags of Turkmenistan are lowered, and thousands of people commemorate this day with sadness and sadness. On that day, tens of thousands of people from all over Turkmenistan came to Goy-Tepe to commemorate the victims of the tragedy, as well as people who fought heroically until the last breath.

Thus, the Turkmen people fell into slavery to the Russian colonialists. However, they did not easily accept this bondage. After the occupation, at the end of the XIX century, Turkmens repeatedly expressed their protest against Russian rule and fought bloody battles.

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